

Economic Freedom as a Driver of ICT Service Exports

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Abstract: Economic freedom as a driver of ICT Service exports

This paper examines whether economic freedom, as measured by the Index of Economic Freedom, has a positive and time-lagged impact on the share of ICT services exports in total service exports, and whether this effect corresponds to a regression coefficient of at least 0,20 per additional score point. The study is based on a dynamic panel data model according to Arellano-Bond using international secondary data, which maps time-delayed effects over up to ten years. The results show time-delayed effects: For lag 1 ($\beta = 0,827$; $p = 0,014$) and lag 3 ($\beta = 0,418$; $p = 0,032$), there is a positive and statistically significant influence that exceeds the required minimum coefficient. The remaining calculated lags are predominantly positive, but not statistically significant. The study thus confirms the hypothesis: an increase in economic freedom by one score point leads to a time-delayed increase in the share of ICT service exports. The result underscores the importance of open, constitutionally stable, and economically free framework conditions for the international competitiveness of digital service sectors and is therefore also relevant to economic policy.

Keywords:

ICT service exports, economic freedom, export influences, digitization, international trade, international competitiveness

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1. Introduction

1.1 Problem Statement

Information and communication technologies (ICT) are a central component of modern economic value creation. In 2023, 47% of all Austrian companies with more than ten employees used advanced technologies such as cloud services, data analytics, and artificial intelligence. The European Union aims for at least 75% of all companies to adopt at least one of these technologies by 2030 (Statistics Austria 2024).

Figure 1: Percentage of companies with more than nine employees using cloud solutions.

Source: (European Commission 2024)

As illustrated in Figure 1, in 2023 at least 40% of companies used cloud solutions in seven of the 27 EU Member States. Across the European Union, the average share of companies with more than nine employees using cloud solutions was 39.9%, representing an increase of 5.9 percentage points compared to 2021 (European Commission 2024).

At the same time, the global volume of ICT service exports increased from less than USD 200 billion in 2004 to more than USD 1.1 trillion in 2023. This development highlights the growing importance of digital services in international trade (World Bank Group 2023).

Figure 2: Development of global ICT service exports in trillion USD.

Source: (World Bank Group 2023)

As illustrated in Figure 2, the volume of ICT service exports was still below USD 200 billion in 2004. By 2023, it exceeded USD 1.1 trillion for the first time, representing more than a fivefold increase within two decades. Growth became particularly dynamic after 2017, with a strong acceleration between 2019 and 2021, indicating the increasing global importance of ICT services in international trade (World Bank Group 2023).

Despite this positive development, substantial differences remain between countries regarding the share of ICT service exports in total service exports. While countries such as China, Ireland, Poland, and Finland recorded strong growth, other countries experienced significantly weaker developments (UNCTAD 2024).

Figure 3: ICT services exports as a percentage share of total service exports.

Source: (UNCTAD 2024)

As shown in Figure 3, China increased the share of ICT service exports in its total service exports by more than 700% between 2005 and 2023. With a share of 23.7% in 2023, China significantly exceeded the EU average of 14.98% and further widened the gap compared to the United States, whose share amounted to 5.81% in the same year.

EU member states such as Ireland, Finland, Poland, Romania, Latvia, and the Czech Republic recorded increases in the share of ICT services of up to 400%. In contrast, countries such as Malta, Greece, and Portugal experienced below-average development. Their growth rates remained well below the EU average of approximately 101.9%, with some countries even recording negative growth trends (UNCTAD 2024).

However, this comparatively low export share does not reflect a lack of market presence, but is partly the result of international corporate structures. Many U.S. technology companies provide digital services through European subsidiaries rather than through direct exports from the United States. Consequently, these revenues are statistically recorded as intra-European transactions rather than as U.S. exports (Allen, et al. 2023).

The growing importance of digital infrastructures simultaneously increases the dependence of European countries on non-European technology companies. Significant dependencies on U.S. and Asian providers exist particularly in areas such as cloud infrastructure, platform services, artificial intelligence, and semiconductor technologies. As a result, issues of digital sovereignty, economic resilience, and institutional frameworks are becoming increasingly important (Glamann, Kriegeskotte und Weber 2025).

1.2 Relevance of the Study

ICT service exports are increasingly regarded as an important driver of economic growth, technological competitiveness, and innovation. Previous studies indicate that rising ICT exports are associated with positive macroeconomic developments such as higher GDP growth, increased productivity, and additional employment opportunities (Oliinyk 2023).

Figure 4: Development of global GDP and ICT service exports, 2005–2021.

Source: (Oliinyk 2023)

Oliinyk argues that ICT service exports influence GDP growth rather than the other way around. This argument is based on the observation that countries with previously low export levels experienced corresponding GDP growth between 2016 and 2021 after increasing their ICT service exports. These patterns are interpreted as an indication of the direction of causality, although definitive causal evidence could not be established (Oliinyk 2023).

Export-oriented ICT sectors create employment opportunities particularly for highly skilled professionals in areas such as software development, data processing, and IT

consulting. As a result, innovation systems can be strengthened and the emigration of qualified labor can be reduced (Ronen 2021).

Furthermore, competitive digital service sectors enable stronger integration into global value chains and increase economic resilience against external shocks. At the same time, limited domestic ICT capabilities may intensify digital dependence on foreign technology providers (Leogrande 2024).

Previous research has examined various determinants of exports, including human capital, institutional quality, trade openness, and macroeconomic conditions. However, the specific relationship between economic freedom and ICT service exports has so far received only limited attention, particularly with regard to time-lagged effects.

1.3 Research Question and Objectives

This study examines whether economic freedom, measured by the *Index of Economic Freedom*, exerts a positive time-lagged effect on the share of ICT service exports in total service exports.

To analyze this relationship, a dynamic panel data model based on the Arellano–Bond estimator is employed in order to capture institutional effects over multiple years. The objective is to empirically assess the influence of economic freedom on the international competitiveness of digital service sectors.

The underlying hypothesis is that a higher degree of economic freedom is associated with a time-lagged increase in the share of ICT service exports.

2. Fundamentals and State of the Art

This chapter explains the key concepts and theoretical foundations relevant to the analysis of ICT service exports and economic freedom. In addition to defining ICT service exports, the institutional framework of international service markets and the statistical measurement of digital services are presented. Furthermore, panel data models and time-lagged effects are discussed as the methodological foundation of the empirical analysis.

2.1 Service Exports

The term “export” refers to the cross-border provision of goods or services to foreign customers. In international trade in services, the World Trade Organization (WTO), within the framework of the *General Agreement on Trade in Services* (GATS), distinguishes between different modes of service supply. These include cross-border digital services, services provided through foreign subsidiaries, and the physical provision of services on-site (Magdeleine und Maurer 2008).

The definition of ICT service exports is based on the international service classification *EBOPS 2010* of the *Balance of Payments and International Investment Position Manual* (BPM6) issued by the International Monetary Fund. The category “Telecommunications, Computer and Information Services” includes cross-border digital services such as software development, cloud services, data processing, hosting, IT consulting, and technical support services (International Monetary Fund 2009).

Unlike traditional merchandise exports, the provision of ICT services is predominantly digital and intangible. Consequently, ICT service exports constitute a central component of modern digital service markets (International Monetary Fund 2009).

2.2 Economic Freedom

Economic freedom describes the extent to which individuals and businesses are able to make economic decisions freely. This includes, in particular, the protection of property rights, investment freedom, trade freedom, as well as limited regulatory and governmental intervention in economic activities.

To measure economic freedom, this study uses the *Index of Economic Freedom* published by the Heritage Foundation. The index evaluates more than 180 countries on the basis of twelve equally weighted indicators assigned to four categories: rule of law,

government size, regulatory efficiency, and market openness (Heritage Foundation 2025).

The individual indicators include, among others, property rights, business freedom, trade freedom, investment freedom, and financial freedom. Each indicator is scored on a scale from 0 to 100, where higher values represent a higher degree of economic freedom. The overall score is calculated as the average of all twelve indicators and serves as an internationally comparable measure of institutional and economic policy conditions.

2.3 Measurement of ICT Service Exports

Within the framework of the *World Development Indicators*, the World Bank measures the share of ICT service exports in a country's total service exports. The underlying data are based on national balance of payments statistics compiled according to the *Balance of Payments Manual (BPM6)* of the International Monetary Fund (World Bank 2024).

ICT services include telecommunications services, computer services, and information services. These encompass activities such as software development, cloud and hosting services, data processing, IT consulting, and digital information platforms (International Monetary Fund 2009).

The ICT export ratio is calculated as the share of ICT service exports in a country's total service exports. For international comparisons, the World Bank applies weighted averages, meaning that countries with higher export volumes have a greater influence on the overall calculation (World Bank 2024).

2.4 Panel Data

Panel data consist of observations of multiple entities over several time periods. They enable the analysis of temporal developments and the control of unobservable country-specific differences (Arellano und Bond 1991).

Classical panel data models commonly apply either fixed-effects or random-effects approaches. In fixed-effects models, unobserved individual effects are removed through transformations, whereas the random-effects approach assumes that these effects are not correlated with the explanatory variables (Arellano und Bond 1991).

Dynamic panel data models extend this framework by including lagged dependent variables. This allows the analysis to account for the fact that current developments may partly depend on previous states. In the context of this study, this implies that the share of ICT service exports of a country may also be influenced by its past export levels.

To estimate dynamic panel data models, the Arellano–Bond estimator is applied. This method uses lagged values of the dependent variable as instruments in order to reduce endogeneity problems and obtain consistent estimates (Arellano und Bond 1991).

2.5 Time-Lagged Effects

Economic determinants often do not exert their effects immediately, but rather with a temporal delay. Such relationships are described by distributed lag models, in which the impact of an independent variable is distributed across multiple periods (Stock und Watson 2015).

Accounting for these time-lagged effects enables a more realistic representation of economic dynamics and therefore constitutes a central component of the empirical analysis conducted in this study (Stock und Watson 2015).

3. Current State of Research and Previous Studies

This chapter summarizes key theoretical and empirical studies that explain the relationship between international exports, digital services, institutional frameworks, and economic freedom. The focus is placed on studies that are particularly relevant for the analysis of ICT service exports and time-lagged effects.

3.1 Theoretical Foundations of International Trade

Classical trade theory according to Ricardo explains international specialization through comparative advantages. According to this approach, countries benefit from trade when they specialize in goods or services for which they have lower relative opportunity costs. In the context of digital services, this implies that countries with suitable institutional, technological, and human capital conditions can develop competitive advantages (Batoche Books 2001).

The New Trade Theory developed by Krugman extends this perspective by emphasizing economies of scale, market size, and product differentiation as central drivers of trade. Digital services particularly benefit from low marginal costs, international scalability, and access to large markets. Krugman's theory therefore provides an important foundation for explaining international digital service markets (Krugman 1979).

The Melitz model complements this perspective at the firm level. It demonstrates that primarily highly productive firms are capable of bearing the fixed costs associated with exporting and serving international markets. In this context, trade liberalization acts as a selection mechanism through which more productive firms gain market share, thereby increasing average industry productivity. This is particularly relevant for knowledge-intensive and export-oriented ICT sectors (Andrew und Bradford 1999).

3.2 Empirical Studies

Empirical studies show that ICT and software exports are influenced by various macroeconomic and structural factors. Malik and Velan examine the development of Indian software and IT service exports and demonstrate that external demand, human capital, and openness exert significantly positive effects on export performance. Particularly relevant is their use of a dynamic model, as it allows both short-term and long-term relationships to be taken into account (Malik und Velan 2020).

Jacob and Raphael likewise show that macroeconomic conditions such as exchange rates and inflation can have both short-term and long-term effects on export volumes. Their study highlights that export developments are shaped not only by immediate effects but also by time-lagged adjustment processes (Jacob und Raphael 2021).

Human capital represents another key determinant of exports. Mulliqi demonstrates for 27 European countries that a higher share of tertiary-educated individuals is positively associated with technology-intensive exports. This underlines the importance of qualified labor for knowledge-intensive and digital export sectors (Mulliqi, 2021). In addition, Kumar and Mazhar show that international demand, export strategies, networks, and highly skilled professionals have contributed substantially to the success of Indian software service exports (Kumar und Mazhar 2022).

3.3 Institutional and Regulatory Frameworks

In addition to macroeconomic and human-capital-related factors, institutional frameworks play a central role in the export of digital services. In their study, Wang, Zhang, and Zhu examine regulatory barriers in digital trade in services and demonstrate that institutional restrictions can affect the export efficiency of digital services. Their findings highlight that regulatory quality and digital trade conditions are important determinants of international competitiveness (Wang, Zhang und Zhu 2024).

Ghosh, Gupta, and Sridhar analyze the impact of data restrictions on ICT service exports and identify a negative relationship between regulatory constraints on data flows and export performance. Their study illustrates that institutional openness and reliable digital frameworks are essential for international trade in ICT services (Ghosh, Gupta und Sridhar 2022).

A similar perspective is provided by Wang, Meng, and Liu, who investigate the influence of digital trade conditions in importing countries on technology-intensive exports. Their results show that advanced digital and institutional frameworks in destination countries can positively affect export performance. This complements the perspective of the present study, which focuses on economic freedom in the exporting country (Liu, Meng und Wang 2025).

3.4 The Impact of Economic Freedom on Economic Growth

Several studies examine the relationship between economic freedom and macroeconomic development. Brkić et al. show, based on evidence from European

countries, that changes in economic freedom can have a positive effect on economic growth, particularly through investment activity. However, the magnitude of this effect varies depending on the institutional and structural environment (Brkic, Dukic Marija und Radenovic Tijana 2020).

Nguyen et al. likewise confirm a positive relationship between economic freedom and economic growth. Their findings further indicate that the effect of economic freedom depends on the quality of regulatory institutions. This demonstrates that economic freedom does not operate in isolation, but rather in interaction with other institutional conditions (Chu, Nguyen und Tran 2024).

This line of research is particularly relevant for the present study, as the analysis does not focus on the general effect of economic freedom on economic growth, but specifically on the share of ICT service exports. In doing so, the existing body of research is extended to a digital and export-oriented sector.

3.5 Digital Dependence

The issue of digital export capability is also highly relevant in the context of digital dependence. Using the *Digital Dependence Index*, Lu and Mayer demonstrate that many European countries are highly dependent on foreign digital technologies, platforms, and infrastructures. In particular, Europe exhibits a dual dependence on Chinese ICT goods and U.S. platform and infrastructure services (Lu und Mayer 2023).

These findings illustrate that strengthening the domestic ICT service sector is not only of economic importance, but also of strategic relevance. Greater digital export capability can contribute to technological sovereignty, economic resilience, and international competitiveness

3.6 Measurement of Economic Freedom

For the empirical analysis, the question arises as to whether economic freedom should be measured as an aggregate index or through individual sub-indicators. Lawson argues that economic freedom should be understood as an integrated institutional system. Individual components such as property rights, trade freedom, or investment freedom do not operate in isolation, but derive their significance through interaction with one another. Consequently, the aggregate index may provide more robust and consistent results (Lawson 2022).

However, Heckelman and Stroup point out that composite freedom indices may be problematic if individual components exert different or even opposing effects on the dependent variable under investigation. They therefore recommend critically reflecting on the composition of such indices (Heckelman und Stroup 2005).

Nevertheless, this study employs the aggregate index, as the focus lies on economic freedom as a broader institutional framework. At the same time, the potential limitations of aggregated index values are taken into account when interpreting the results.

4. Methodological Approach

4.1 Use of Relative Values

To examine the relationship between economic freedom and ICT service exports, relative rather than absolute export values are used. Specifically, the analysis focuses on the share of ICT service exports in a country's total service exports.

The use of relative values enables international comparability by reducing differences arising from the size of national economies and overall export volumes. This approach also allows smaller but highly specialized countries such as Estonia or Finland to be adequately represented. In contrast, absolute export values would favor large economies such as China or the United States, even though the ICT sector in these countries may account for only a relatively small share of total exports.

Relative values further allow for an analysis of the structural importance of the ICT sector within a country's overall export structure. A high share indicates a stronger specialization in ICT services, regardless of the absolute export volume.

Since the present study focuses on the structural role of ICT service exports rather than their absolute trade volume, relative export shares are used as the dependent variable.

4.2 Data Basis

The empirical analysis is based on secondary data from the *Index of Economic Freedom* published by the Heritage Foundation, as well as World Bank data on ICT service exports as a share of total service exports.

The use of secondary data enables the analysis of long-term developments across numerous countries while ensuring a high degree of international comparability. The selected data sources are based on standardized collection and classification procedures and are widely used in economic research.

Since the research question examines macroeconomic and institutional relationships over extended periods of time, the collection of primary data would neither be practical nor suitable for providing sufficiently comprehensive and internationally comparable data

4.3 Model Selection

To analyze the relationship between economic freedom and ICT service exports, a dynamic panel data model is employed. This model allows the simultaneous consideration of temporal developments within individual countries as well as structural differences between countries.

A major advantage of dynamic panel models is their ability to explicitly capture time-lagged effects. This makes it possible to examine whether changes in economic freedom affect ICT service exports only after several years.

In addition, the model controls for unobserved, time-invariant country-specific effects, such as institutional or geographical differences, which cannot be adequately addressed in conventional cross-sectional or time-series models.

For the present research question, static models such as fixed-effects or random-effects approaches are only of limited suitability, as they do not sufficiently account for persistence effects and potential endogeneity. Pure time-series models, on the other hand, do not allow for comparable cross-country analysis. Therefore, the dynamic panel data model represents the most appropriate approach for examining time-lagged institutional effects.

4.4 Method Selection

To estimate the dynamic panel data model, the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) estimator developed by Arellano and Bond is applied. This method is particularly suitable for panel datasets with a large number of cross-sectional units and a limited time dimension, as well as for models including lagged dependent variables (Arellano und Bond 1991).

A major advantage of the GMM estimator is its ability to reduce potential endogeneity problems. For this purpose, lagged values of the dependent variable are used as internal instruments. This approach allows for more consistent estimates than classical OLS or fixed-effects estimators, which may produce biased results in dynamic panel models.

In contrast to the System GMM approach, this study applies the more robust Difference GMM variant. This method reduces problems associated with weak instruments and

overidentification, which may occur particularly in panels with a large number of countries.

Accordingly, the selected method enables the analysis of time-lagged relationships between economic freedom and ICT service exports while accounting for unobserved heterogeneity and dynamic effects.

5. Application of the Method

5.1 Data Basis and Sample

The empirical analysis is based on two datasets: ICT service export data from the World Bank and the *Index of Economic Freedom* published by the Heritage Foundation. Since the two datasets differ with regard to time coverage and country coverage, a common database was first constructed.

Figure 5: Time coverage of the datasets.

Source: Authors' own illustration

The ICT service export data cover the period from 1975 to 2024, while the economic freedom data are available for the period from 1995 to 2024. Therefore, the common observation period beginning in 1995 was initially selected for the analysis. Subsequently, the intersection of countries included in both datasets was identified.

Figure 6: Venn diagram of the country intersection analysis.

Source: Authors' own illustration

Since complete values for both variables are not available for every country and every year, an interval analysis was additionally conducted. The objective was to determine a study period that provides both a sufficiently long time series and the broadest possible country coverage. For this purpose, all possible time intervals between 1995 and 2024 were examined and evaluated according to three criteria: maximum time span, maximum number of countries, and maximum number of valid observations.

The results reveal a trade-off between temporal depth and country coverage. The longest complete interval, from 1995 to 2024, includes 40 countries and 1,200 observations. The interval with the highest number of observations covers the period from 2000 to 2022 and contains 90 countries with 2,070 observations. However, for the subsequent analysis, the interval from 1997 to 2023 was selected, as it represents a balanced compromise between observation period, data completeness, and country coverage, comprising 73 countries and 1,971 observations.

The final dataset contains, for each country and year, the share of ICT service exports in total service exports as well as the corresponding economic freedom score.

5.2 Arellano-Bond GMM Estimation

For the empirical analysis, a dynamic panel data model based on the Arellano–Bond estimator is applied. The model accounts for the persistence of the dependent variable as well as the time-lagged effects of economic freedom on the share of ICT service exports.

A central issue in dynamic panel models is that the lagged dependent variable may be correlated with unobserved country-specific effects. To avoid this bias, the model is estimated in first differences, thereby eliminating time-invariant country-specific effects.

Since differencing may still lead to endogeneity problems, the Arellano–Bond approach uses lagged values of the variables as internal instruments. This instrumentation allows for more consistent estimates, provided that the instruments are valid and uncorrelated with the error terms.

The estimation is conducted using a Difference GMM model. To examine whether and after how many years a statistically significant effect emerges, a separate model is estimated for each lag of the economic freedom variable.

5.3 Model Validation

Several diagnostic tests are applied to evaluate the validity of the model. The Arellano–Bond first-order autocorrelation test (AR(1)) examines short-term autocorrelation in the differenced error terms. Since the model is estimated in first differences, a significant AR(1) test is expected and does not indicate a problem.

The crucial diagnostic is the Arellano–Bond second-order autocorrelation test (AR(2)). A non-significant AR(2) test indicates the absence of invalid second-order autocorrelation and therefore suggests that the instrumentation is generally consistent.

In addition, the Hansen test is employed to assess the validity of the instrumental variables. A non-significant Hansen test indicates that the instruments are exogenous. In contrast, very low or very high p-values may point to problems with the instruments or to model overfitting.

In this study, an estimation is considered diagnostically valid if the AR(2) test is not significant and the Hansen test falls within an acceptable range.

5.4 Specifacation of the Lag Structure

To investigate time-lagged effects, economic freedom is incorporated into the model using different lag lengths. Separate Arellano–Bond models are estimated for each lag ranging from one to ten years.

The coefficients of the lagged economic freedom variable indicate whether and to what extent changes in economic freedom are associated with subsequent changes in the share of ICT service exports. A positive coefficient suggests a positive relationship, while a statistically significant coefficient indicates a robust statistical effect.

Three criteria are applied to evaluate the hypothesis: a positive regression coefficient, statistical significance at the 5% level, and successful diagnostic tests. In addition, it is examined whether the coefficient reaches at least 0.20, as this corresponds to the effect threshold defined in the research question.

6. Results

6.1 Presentation of the Results

The results of the Arellano–Bond estimation show that the effect of economic freedom on the share of ICT service exports varies depending on the time lag considered.

Figure 7: Impact of economic freedom on the share of ICT service exports.

Lag	Beta (β)	SE	p	AR(1)-p	AR(2)-p	Hansen-p
1	0,827	0,338	0,014	0,014	0,574	0,777
2	-0,016	0,034	0,628	0,007	0,305	0,305
3	0,418	0,195	0,032	0,121	0,376	0,368
4	0,448	0,701	0,523	0,136	0,241	0,331
5	0,165	0,258	0,522	0,075	0,274	0,330
6	1,166	0,890	0,191	0,696	0,147	0,695
7	0,302	1,559	0,846	0,309	0,443	0,732
8	0,705	1,197	0,556	0,631	0,791	0,678
9	0,352	2,288	0,878	0,475	0,458	0,729
10	0,775	0,866	0,371	0,595	0,685	0,927

Source: Authors' own illustration

In the first lag, a positive and statistically significant coefficient of $\beta = 0.827$ is observed, with a p-value of 0.014. The estimated effect therefore exceeds the predefined threshold of 0.20 and remains below the 5% significance level. This indicates that an increase in economic freedom is associated with a time-lagged rise in the share of ICT service exports.

A positive and statistically significant effect is also found in the third lag. The coefficient amounts to $\beta = 0.418$ with a p-value of 0.032, thus likewise exceeding the defined minimum threshold of 0.20.

These findings suggest that economic freedom can exert a positive influence on the export structure of digital services not only in the short term, but also with a medium-term delay.

For the remaining lags, the coefficients are predominantly positive but statistically insignificant. In particular, the sixth lag exhibits a comparatively high coefficient of $\beta = 1.166$; however, due to the large standard error and the p-value of 0.191, this estimate cannot be interpreted as statistically reliable. From the fourth lag onward, statistical uncertainty generally increases, indicating lower estimation stability for longer lag structures.

Overall, the results show that the relationship between economic freedom and ICT service exports becomes particularly visible during the first years following changes in economic conditions. The effect appears clearly in the first lag, re-emerges in the third lag, and subsequently loses statistical significance.

Figure 8: Regression coefficients by lag length.

Source: Authors' own illustration

6.2 Model Validation

Overall, the diagnostic tests support the validity of the model specification. The AR(1) tests are partially significant, which is expected in estimations based on first differences and does not constitute a problem in itself.

The crucial diagnostic is the AR(2) test. Across all estimated lags, the AR(2) p-values remain above the conventional significance threshold of 0.05, indicating no evidence of problematic second-order autocorrelation. This supports the consistency of the applied instrumentation.

The Hansen p-values also mostly fall within an acceptable range. They suggest that the instruments used are generally valid and that there is no clear evidence of overidentification. However, the Hansen value for the tenth lag, at 0.927, lies close to the upper boundary and should therefore be interpreted with caution.

Overall, the models satisfy the central diagnostic requirements of the Arellano–Bond procedure. The statistically significant results obtained for the first and third lag can therefore be regarded as methodologically robust.

7. Conclusion

7.1 Answering the Research Question

The objective of this study was to examine whether economic freedom, measured by the *Index of Economic Freedom*, exerts a positive and time-lagged effect on the share of ICT service exports in total service exports, and whether this effect corresponds to a regression coefficient of at least 0.20 per additional score point.

The results of the dynamic panel data analysis demonstrate that economic freedom has a positive and time-lagged effect on ICT service exports. In particular, statistically significant effects are identified in the first lag ($\beta = 0.827$; $p = 0.014$) and the third lag ($\beta = 0.418$; $p = 0.032$), both of which clearly exceed the predefined threshold value of 0.20.

The research question can therefore be answered in the affirmative. The findings indicate that an increase in economic freedom is associated with a subsequent rise in the share of ICT service exports. At the same time, the results suggest that this effect occurs primarily in the short to medium term and loses stability as the temporal distance increases.

7.2 Evaluation of the Hypothesis

The hypothesis underlying this study is as follows:

“Economic freedom (measured by the *Index of Economic Freedom*) exerts a positive, time-lagged effect on the share of ICT service exports. An increase in economic freedom by one score point corresponds to a regression coefficient of at least 0.20.”

The empirical findings confirm this hypothesis. Across several lag structures, a positive effect of economic freedom on ICT service exports can be observed. In particular, the estimated coefficients in the first and third lag exceed both the predefined minimum threshold and the 5% significance level.

Accordingly, the hypothesis can be confirmed for short-term and medium-term lags. The results suggest that economic freedom represents a relevant institutional determinant for the development of ICT service exports.

8. Summary and Outlook

8.1 Summary

This study examined the relationship between economic freedom and the share of ICT service exports in total service exports. The starting point was the observation that, despite increasing digitalization and growing global demand for digital services, countries have developed very differently.

To investigate this relationship, a dynamic panel data model based on the Arellano–Bond estimator was applied. The analysis was based on international secondary data from the World Bank and the Heritage Foundation covering 73 countries over the period from 1997 to 2023.

The results show that economic freedom exerts a positive but time-lagged effect on ICT service exports. In particular, statistically significant effects were identified in the first and third lag. The diagnostic tests confirm the methodological robustness of the model as well as the validity of the instruments used.

The findings therefore highlight the importance of institutional frameworks for the international competitiveness of digital service sectors. Open markets, regulatory stability, and economic freedom can create favorable conditions for export-oriented digital services.

8.2 Outlook

The findings of this study open several avenues for future research. One important area concerns a more detailed investigation of the individual components of economic freedom. While this study employed the aggregate index, future research could analyze which specific dimensions—such as property rights, tax policy, or market openness—are particularly relevant for digital service exports.

Furthermore, the results indicate that the influence of economic freedom is limited and loses stability over longer lag structures. Future studies could therefore examine which additional factors shape long-term export developments. Possible candidates include interactions with human capital, innovation capacity, digitalization, or international connectivity.

Methodologically, several extensions are also conceivable. In addition to Difference GMM, future studies could apply System GMM models, interaction effects, or nonlinear approaches in order to capture more complex relationships. Likewise, causal inference methods could be employed to further test the robustness of the results with regard to endogeneity and unobserved influencing factors.

In addition, sectoral and regional extensions offer promising directions for further analysis. Developed economies, emerging markets, or digitally advanced countries could be examined separately. The analysis could also be extended to specific areas such as AI services, cloud services, or software exports.

Overall, this study demonstrates that institutional frameworks can make a relevant contribution to the development of digital export sectors. At the same time, the findings highlight the complexity of economic processes and the wide range of additional factors influencing the international competitiveness of digital services.

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